

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

NORMATIVE AND ACTUAL INDICATORS AND THEIR DEFICITS IN TEASUITABLE SOILS OF HUMID SUBTROPICS OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

In the article, on the basis of many years of scientific research, the current state of the fertility of tea soils in the humid subtropics of Azerbaijan is considered. The main indicators of fertility, the amount of humus, total nitrogen, phosphorus, the amount of absorbed bases and the actual indicators of the reaction of the soil environment (pH) are compared with the standard level of these indicators. According to the research results, the deficit of the main soil indicators that determine soil fertility is determined.

Keywords: soil, fertility, defisit, humus, nitrogen

Introduction

Protecting and increasing soil fertility is of great importance in providing the country's population with food and creating a solid fodder base for livestock. The problems of soil fertility and its solution are one of the important issues in the constant focus of the Azerbaijan. The Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Land Fertility" was adopted on December 30, 1999 (17). In order to achieve the goals set by the law, the country's scientists have great tasks. Employees of the Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry of ANAS carry out fundamental research work on several topics related to soil fertility (11,15).

R.V.Kovalyov (7, 8), B.I.Hasanov (5, 6), D.R.Ahadov (1, 2) A.H.Valiyev (4), S.Z.Mammadova (9) and others, who studied the soils of the humid subtropical region, in the humid subtropical region of Azerbaijan in the transition to yellow soil brown, mountain-forest yellow, podzol mountain-forest yellow, podzolic yellow at different levels, superficial, deep gleyed or clayic podzolic yellow soils It is proposed to cultivate a tea bush (Table 1). In general, river lands are distributed in the lowlands Terrace IV of the, in the foothills of the III Terrace and in the mountainous and forested areas of the Caspian Sea where it was raised for the second time. The lands of Lankaran, Astara, Masalli districts and the eastern part of Lerik district are considered tea-suitable lands.

Methodology

R.V Kovalyov (7, 8) with his researches determined that the total area of tea lands is 26100 ha. Hectares of these lands belong to groups I and II in

terms of quality, and these areas were also recommended primarily for tea cultivation. In addition, 10000 ha of group III lands can be used under tea plantations after certain agrochemical and agro-technical measures. It should be noted that during the USSR, more than 13400 hectares of this land were under tea plantations. During the period of homelessness, chaos and anarchy in the USSR near the end of the twentieth century, these tea plantations were deliberately dismantled and used under faster and more profitable vegetable crops and legumes.

At the time of the agrarian reforms, there were only 2900 hectares of tea plantations left in the country. After the implementation of land reforms, the villagers, who became landowners, realized the importance of tea growing, albeit belatedly, and took an active part in the development of this field, and now the interest in this field is growing. As a result, the area of tea plantations in Azerbaijan increased to 7473 hectares in a short time. As a result of neglect, teabushes in Balakan, Gakh and Lerik districts were completely destroyed, leaving 89 ha of plantations in Zagatala district alone.

In the tea-prone areas of the subtropical region, mountain-forest yellow, mountain-forest podzolic yellow, podzolic yellow and podzolic clay and podzolic clayic yellow soils with different degrees of transition to yellow soil were formed. In some of these soil types, a hardened B layer is found, which leads to the accumulation of unfiltered water from the top layer in the upper layers. Under the resulting anaerobic conditions, tea bushes and citrus plants cannot grow normally. Depending on the plasticity of the soil,

different types of soil with different mechanical composition have been formed in the soil types distributed in the area (11, 14, 16).

In the morphogenetic diagnostics, nomenclature and classification of Azerbaijani soils prepared by the Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry (MP Babayev, V.H. Hasanov, Ch.M. Jafarova and S.M. Huseynova (3) these soils were distinguished as separate types and subtypes.

Mountain-forest yellow, mountain-forest brown, transfer to yellow? podzolic mountain-forest yellow soils can be classified as Alfisols in the World soil classification, and podzole and dopodzolly-clay yellow soils can be referred to as Oxisols.

Main part

Summarizing the results of studies on humus and essential nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium), which are the main indicators of soil fertility, the level of fertility of subtropical soils is not enough good in some soil types and subtypes. Especially in the 0-50 cm layer of soil, the process of podzolization occurs as a result of the transfer of nutrients to the lower layers. The large amount of precipitation (800-1300 mm) also plays a big role in this process. In the upper A horizon of washed mountain-forest brown to transver yellow soil, typical mountain-forest yellow soils, humus deficiency (deficit) is more (1.70-2.41%). In the 0-50 and 0-100 cm layer of soils, these indicators are in line with the norm, and in some soils in the 100 cm layer is between 0.02-0.69%. However, total nitrogen deficiency is observed in all soils of the studied area (0.006-0.094%), which indicates an abnormality in the ratio of humus to nitrogen (Table 1). As can be seen, the high content of humus and nitrogen in the lower layers of the soil, or even higher than the norm, is due to the fact that the lower layers of these substances are washed away during the podzolization process. Depending on the degree of podzolization, the amount of absorbed bases (Ca, Mg, Na, H), which play a special role in the formation of soil structure, also varies along the profile, and this indicator is almost normal or above normal for

most soil types and subtypes. Only in mountain-forest yellow (-8.83%), deep clayey podzolic yellow (-6.4%) and surface and deep clayey yellow (-11.38%) soils there is a lack of absorbed bases.

Environmental reaction indicators (pH) of tea-producing soils are the main factor influencing the development of tea bushes and subtropical plants. The environment of all subtropical soils is quite acidic and there is no such deficit in the area. These indicators are better than normative ones. In some subtypes the acidity is slightly less (0.5-0.6).

Prolonged non-application of crop rotation system in lands, improper observance of agro-technical rules, poor application of chemicals are the main reasons for low fertility (Diagrams 1 and 2).

Agrotechnical rules must be followed to increase the amount of humus and nitrogen in the topsoil. In order to form humus and nitrogen in the soil, siderate crops should be rotated every three years by applying a rotating cropping system, and siderate crops, cereals and legumes should be planted and rested on these lands. By accumulating nitrogen in the air through the leaves of these plants, they stimulate the formation of nitrogen tubers in the root system and the spread of nitrogen accumulated in the tubers to the planting and plowing layer during cultivation. In addition, in order to increase soil fertility, it is important to apply nitrogen fertilizers along with the seeds at the time of sowing, during the period of plant emergence and germination. In order to improve the structure of the soil and increase the amount of Ca and Mg cautions in the absorbed bases, the application of superphosphate fertilizers should be given wide coverage.

In the correct formation of the soil structure, immediately after the collection of agricultural crops, the soil should be plowed to a depth of 20-25 cm during the period when there are residues of straw and other plant mass in the soil. This will help increase the amount of Ca and Mg in the soil, as well as maintain moisture in the lower layers.

Table 1
The main indicators of fertility of tea lands of humid subtropics of Azerbaijan

Soil types and subtypes	Fertility indicators of soil											
	humus, %			Total nitrogen, %			Sum of absorbed cations (Ca, Mg, Na, H), mg-ekv-lb			pH aguenses suspension		
	0-20	0-50	0-100	0-20	0-50	0-100	0-20	0-50	0-100	0-20	0-50	0-100
Mountain-forest brown transferred to yellow (jeltozem)	N	5,00	3,00	2,00	0,350	0,200	35,00	30,00	28,00	6,9	7,0	7,2
	F	4,74	3,80	2,42	0,396	0,219	39,05	28,50	22,25	6,4	6,3	6,6
	D	-0,26	+0,80	+0,42	+0,046	+0,019	+4,05	-1,50	-5,75	-0,5	-0,7	-0,6
Mountain-forest yellow (jeltozem)	N	6,00	2,50	2,00	0,350	0,200	37,00	30,00	24,00	6,5	6,5	6,5
	F	4,15	2,42	1,53	0,236	0,174	36,61	32,62	32,16	6,7	5,8	5,8
	D	-0,85	-0,02	-0,47	-0,094	-0,026	-0,39	+2,620	+8,16	+0,2	-0,7	-0,7
Mountain-forest podzolized yellow (jeltozem)	N	6,00	3,00	1,50	0,300	0,200	35,00	28,00	24,00	5,6	5,8	5,8
	F	6,16	3,25	1,80	0,232	0,109	26,17	26,94	28,50	6,1	5,9	5,8
	D	+0,16	+0,25	+0,30	-0,068	-0,091	-8,83	-1,04	+5,50	+0,5	+0,1	0,0
Slightly podzolic yellow	N	4,00	2,50	1,50	0,250	0,150	35,00	35,00	35,00	6,5	6,5	6,5
	F	3,38	2,46	1,72	0,176	0,127	28,02	28,02	28,72	6,0	5,9	5,9
	D	-0,62	-0,04	+0,22	-0,074	-0,023	-6,98	-6,98	-6,28	-0,5	-0,6	-0,6
Medium podzolic yellow (jeltozem)	N	3,00	1,50	0,80	0,250	0,150	35,00	30,00	25,00	6,8	6,3	6,0
	F	2,30	1,79	0,60	0,214	0,144	31,15	33,46	26,78	6,1	6,4	6,6
	D	-0,70	+0,14	-0,20	-0,036	-0,006	-3,85	+3,46	+1,78	-0,7	+0,1	+0,6
Strongly podzolic yellow (jeltozem)	N	3,50	2,00	1,00	0,250	0,150	35,00	32,00	27,00	5,5	5,6	5,5
	F	4,84	2,68	1,14	0,349	0,166	34,60	34,78	36,25	5,3	5,3	5,4
	D	+1,44	+0,68	+0,14	+0,099	+0,016	-0,40	+2,78	+9,25	-0,2	-0,3	-0,1
Podzolic suprefineally gley yellow (Jeltozem)	N	4,00	2,50	1,00	0,200	0,150	35,00	34,00	34,00	5,6	5,6	6,0
	F	3,06	2,34	1,78	0,269	0,143	35,76	35,76	30,01	5,6	5,6	6,0
	D	-0,94	-0,16	+0,78	+0,069	-0,007	+0,76	+1,76	-3,99	0,0	0,0	0,0
Podzolic deepgley yellow (Jeltozem)	N	3,00	2,00	1,00	0,200	0,150	40,00	35,00	32,00	6,0	6,0	6,5
	F	2,61	2,38	1,82	0,270	0,199	33,60	32,32	29,70	6,3	6,3	6,2
	D	-0,39	+38	+0,81	+0,070	+0,049	-6,40	-2,68	-2,30	+0,3	+0,3	-0,3
Podzolic superficially and deep gley yellow (Jeltozem)	N	3,00	2,00	1,50	0,200	0,130	38,00	30,00	27,00	6,8	6,8	6,5
	F	3,15	2,36	1,90	0,218	0,159	26,62	26,79	27,16	5,8	5,8	5,5
	D	+0,15	+0,36	+0,40	+0,018	+0,029	-11,38	-3,21	+0,84	-1,0	-1,0	-1,0
Podzolic superficially gleyed yellow (Jeltozem)	N	3,00	2,00	1,50	0,200	0,120	28,00	36,00	25,00	6,7	6,7	6,5
	F	2,01	2,09	1,43	0,158	0,157	37,80	37,00	31,89	5,5	5,5	5,7
	D	-0,99	+0,09	-0,07	-0,042	+0,037	-0,20	+1,00	+6,89	-1,2	-1,2	-0,8
Podzolic deep gleyed yellow (Jeltozem)	N	3,00	2,00	1,50	0,200	0,130	30,00	28,00	25,00	6,8	6,8	6,3
	F	1,99	1,31	2,44	0,196	0,132	36,46	37,93	27,69	4,8	4,8	5,6
	D	1,01	-0,69	+0,94	-0,004	+0,002	+6,46	+9,93	+2,69	-2,0	-2,0	-0,7
Podzolic superficially and deep gleyed yellow (jeltozem)	N	3,00	2,00	1,50	0,200	0,150	26,00	27,00	25,00	6,7	6,7	6,0
	F	3,00	1,37	2,44	0,209	0,179	39,83	35,66	31,92	4,7	4,7	6,6
	D	0,00	-0,63	+0,94	+0,009	+0,029	+13,83	+8,60	+6,92	-2,0	-2,0	+0,6

P,S: N – normative indicators F – actual indicators, D – deficits

Normative and actual indicators of humus and their deficits in teasuitable soils of humid subtropics of Azerbaijan

Diagram 1

Row 1 0-20 sm. normative indicators, %
 Row 3 0-50 sm. normative indicators, %
 Row 5 0-100 sm. normative indicators,
 Row 2 0-20 sm. actual indicators, %
 Row 4 0-50 sm. actual indicators, %
 Row 6 0-100 sm. actual indicators, %

Normative and actual indicators of total nitrogens and their deficits in teasuitable soils of humid subtropics of Azerbaijan

Diagram 2
 Row 1 Total nitrogen 0-20 sm, %
 Row 2 Total nitrogen 0-20 sm, %
 Row 3 Total nitrogen 0-50 sm, %
 Row 4 Total nitrogen 0-50 sm, %

Normative and actual levels pH in aguesus suspension and their deficit in teasuitable soils of humid subtropics of Azerbaijan

Normative and actual levels pH in agueses suspension

Row 1 Normative level pH in 0-20 sm.
 Row 2 Actual level pH in 0-20 sm.
 Row 3 Normative level pH in 0-50 sm.
 Row 4 Actual level pH in 0-50 sm.
 Row 5 Normative level pH in 0-100 sm.
 Row 6 Actual level pH in 0-100 sm.

Diagram 4

During agrochemical measures, 500-700 kg (90-120 kg of active substance) superphosphate fertilizers per hectare should be applied to the plowing layer every two years.

Soil reaction (pH) plays a greater role than other indicators of fertility for the growth and high yield of tea and citrus plants, especially in the humid subtropical region. The best pH value for tea cultivation is 5.2 in water suspension. In mountain-forest podzolized yellow, podzolized yellow and podzolized-clay yellow soils, the pH values are in accordance with the norm (14,15).

Findings

In the USSR, soil fertility in the humid subtropics was to some extent protected by cultivating large tracts of land, applying crop rotation, and resting the soil. Fertility was restored through the application of organic and mineral fertilizers, which are nutrients absorbed by plants from the soil. With the land reform implemented in the country, 3.93 mln. ha of lands are divided into three forms of ownership (state, municipal and private).

In this region, a small part of arable land remained in the state (0.2 million hectares), 2.03 million hectares. ha was given to the municipal property. 1.7 million hectares of lands suitable for agriculture, especially under arable and perennial crops. hectares (96%) 875 mln. transferred to the private property of the citizen. In addition, more than 0,3 mln/ hectares of backyard land, which were legally used by citizens, were transferred to their ownership (10, 11). The small size of land shares in most places has significantly reduced the efficiency of their cultivation. The application of agricultural machinery on small plots of land has become more difficult, and their maneuverability has decreased. Later, as a result of land consolidation, the country's low-income peasants switched to collective land use by consolidating their land shares. As a result, the territory of farmers has significantly expanded, due to the expansion of maneuverability of tractors, combine harvester and other agricultural machinery, the fertility of these lands has been preserved and productivity has increased due to the implementation of agro-technical and chemical measures. On the other hand, due to consolidation, the direct and indirect costs incurred by farmers have been significantly reduced and, as a result, they have received more net income (13).

References:

1. Ахадов Д.Р. – «Агроэкологические особенности и бонитировка чаепригодных почв влажных субтропиков южной части Ленкоранской области». Автореферат дисс. канд. с.-х. наук, Баку, 1979, 26 стр.

2. Ахадов Д.Р. - Значение рН как критерии оценки и методы вычисления при бонитировки почв. Доклады АН Азерб. ССР, 1981, Том XXXV, 11, N 3, стр. 70-74.

3. Babayev M.P., Həsənov V.H., Cəfərova Ç.M., Hüseynova S.M. - Azərbaycan torpaqlarının morfoqenetik diaqnostikası, nomenklaturası və təsnifatı. Bakı, 2011, 448 səh.

4. Велиев А.Г. – «Агроэкологические особенности и бонитировка почв агроценозов Ленкоранской области и их рациональное использование». Автореферат дисс. канд. с.-х. наук. Баку, 1981, 25 стр.

5. Гасанов Б.И. – О некоторых особенностях горно-лесных желтоземных почв Ленкоранской области. Доклады АН Азерб.ССР, 1957, № 6. стр. 12-18.

6. Гасанов Б.И. – Подзисто-желтоземных почвы Масаллинского района Азербайджанской ССР, Изв. АН Азерб.ССР, 1957, № 12. стр. 7-12.

7. Ковалев Р.В. – Почвы влажных субтропических районов Азербайджанской ССР в связи с освоением под чай. Изв. АН Азерб.ССР, 1950, № 7, стр. 8-14.

8. Ковалев Р.В. - Почвы Ленкоранской области. Баку, Изд. АН Аз.ССР, 1966, 372 стр.

9. Мамедов Г.Ш. – Основные принципы определения оценки плодородия почв Азербайджана. Изв. АН Аз. ССР, сер. биол.наук, Баку, 1980, № 3, стр. 49-52.

10. Məmmədov Q.Ş. – Azərbaycan Respublikasının Dövlət Torpaq Kadastrı: hüquqi, elmi və praktiki məsələləri. Bakı, 2003. 445 səh.

11. Məmmədov Q.Ş. – Azərbaycanın ekotik problemləri: elmi, hüquqi. Mənəvi aspektləri. Bakı, Elm, 2004, 377 səh.

12. Məmmədov G.Sh. – Agrarian policy of Heydar Aliyev in Azerbaijan, Bakı, Elm, 2013, pp. 333..

13. Məmmədov Q.Ş., Məmmədova S.Z. – Azərbaycanda çayayarırlı torpaqların idarə edilməsi, Bakı, Sabalı, 2018, 37 səh.

14. Мамедова С.З. – Модели плодородия чаепригодных почв Ленкоранской области Азербайджана. Баку, «Элм», 2002, 180 стр.

15. Məmmədova S.Z. – Azərbaycanın Lənkəran vilayəti torpaqlarının ekoloji qiymətləndirilməsi və monitorinqi, Bakı, 2006, 369 səh.

16. Мамедова С.З. – Экономическая оценка, мониторинг почв влажных субтропиков Азербайджана. Lambert, 2016, 284 стр.

17. “Torpaq münbitliyi haqqında” Azərbaycan Respublikasının Qanunu. Bakı, 1999.